

Study of some Transition Metal Complexes of Cephaloridine

PURUSHOTTAM B. CHAKRAWARTI*, BHARATI SRIVASTAVA and B. L. VIJAYVARGIYA

Chemistry Department, Motilal Vigyan Mahavidhyalaya, Bhopal

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Cephaloridine is bactericidal and acts similarly as penicillins. Although much work has been done on the metal complexes of penicillin G and V, practically no work is available on the metal complexes of cephaloridine. Hence the present communication reports the results of our studies on complexation reaction of cephaloridine with some biologically important metal ions.

Results and Discussion

The conductometric¹ and potentiometric (pH) studies indicate that cephaloridine forms 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 complexes with the metal ions.

A perusal of the pH-titration curves indicates liberation of only one proton during complexation of each molecule of the drug,

The study of the formation curves indicates that complexation of cephaloridine takes place in step-wise manner (except Cu^{II}, which involves simultaneous formation of the complexes). The low-values of stability constants (Table 1) show that the interaction of the drug with the metal ions is ionic.

The analytical data (Table 2) indicate that the composition of the complexes is ML₂H₂O. Ir spectra of the complexes indicate that the linking of the drug molecule with the metal ions is through the nitrogen of the β-lactam thiazolidine ring and carboxylate ion forming a five-membered ring. Ir spectra show that, while most of the bands of the ligands remain unchanged on complexation, there

is a considerable shift in the frequencies of tertiary nitrogen of carboxylic group of the ring. The β-lactam amide band in the drugs appearing at

TABLE 1—STABILITY CONSTANTS OF SOME CEPHALORIDINE COMPLEXES

μ = 0.1 M (NaClO₄), Temp. = 30°

Metal(II) complex	log K		log K ₂		log k ₂		ΔG ₁	ΔG ₂	ΔG _n
	(a)	(b)	(a)	(b)	(a)	(b)			
Mg	3.37	3.77	2.05	2.07	5.80	5.84	2.28	1.25	3.53
Mn	4.48	3.55	2.72	2.92	7.20	7.47	2.75	1.77	4.52
Fe	4.72	4.84	3.38	3.32	7.10	7.80	2.93	2.01	4.94
Ni	4.45	4.70	2.70	2.60	7.15	7.39	2.85	1.63	4.48
Co	4.22	4.24	3.69	3.71	7.90	7.95	2.57	2.25	4.82
Zn	4.48	4.46	3.62	3.64	8.10	8.10	2.70	2.20	4.90
K _H	6.91*								

(a)=Graphical method, (b)=least-square method, (*) = pointwise calculation.

TABLE 2—ANALYTICAL DATA OF THE COMPLEXES

Compd./ Colour	M.p. °C	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)					
		Metal	C	H	N	S	H ₂ O
MgL ₂ H ₂ O ^a (Yellow)	126	5.11 (5.13)	48.02 48.14	4.42 4.43	8.84 8.86	13.47 13.51	7.53 7.60
MnL ₂ H ₂ O ^b (Pale yellow)	215	10.86 (10.88)	45.11 45.22	4.15 4.16	8.31 8.33	12.66 12.69	7.12 7.11
FeL ₂ H ₂ O ^b (Dark brown)	>320	11.02 (11.04)	45.03 45.14	4.14 4.15	8.29 8.32	12.64 12.67	7.11 7.12
NiL ₂ H ₂ O ^b (Green)	186	11.52 (11.55)	44.77 44.88	4.12 4.13	8.24 8.26	12.56 12.59	7.06 7.08
CuL ₂ H ₂ O ^a (Dark green)	125	12.35 (12.38)	44.35 44.46	4.08 4.09	8.17 8.19	12.45 12.48	7.00 7.02
ZnL ₂ H ₂ O ^a (Pale yellow)	188	12.65 (12.69)	44.20 44.31	4.07 4.08	8.14 8.16	12.40 12.43	6.97 6.99

^aSparingly soluble in acetone and ethanol. ^bSparingly soluble in acetic acid and acetone.

$\sim 1770\text{ cm}^{-1}$ is shifted to $\sim 1700\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the complexes, while the frequency of ternary N-atom appearing at 1384 cm^{-1} in cephaloridine is shifted to $\sim 1130\text{ cm}^{-1}$. The asymmetric and symmetric COO^- frequencies are shifted from ~ 1614 to $\sim 1630\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and from ~ 1395 to $\sim 1375\text{ cm}^{-1}$ respectively. The difference between asymmetric and symmetric frequencies of COO^- suggests that the complexes have considerable degree of covalency in the metal-oxygen bond. The presence of water finds confirmation² in the band at around 1600 cm^{-1} .

Cephaloridine attacks the peptide bond at two places, viz. D-ala and D-ala-D-ala (ala=alanine). The O-CN bond in the β -lactam ring of cephaloridine is in the same position as the peptide bond in D-ala-D-ala, which splits during transpeptidation³. Divalent metal ions play an important role in the activity of transpeptidase enzyme. It has been proposed that metal-bridged enzyme-drug complex is formed during inhibition activity.

The results indicate that a maximum of two molecules of drug link with the biologically active divalent metal ion. Hence, at least two coordination positions (out of six) of the metal ions are left uncoordinated. These may be utilised in binding the metal-drug complex with the enzymes, resulting in the observed bacteriocidal action.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of A.R. grade.

Stoichiometry of the complexes formed was ascertained by conductometric titrations¹, while Calvin-Bjerrum's pH-titration technique as adopted by Irving and Rossotti⁴ was used for determining the proton-ligand and metal-ligand formation constants at 30° and 0.1 M (NaClO_4) ionic concentration.

The experimental details and the methods of standardisation of solutions were the same as reported earlier⁵.

Zinc, copper, iron and manganese complexes were prepared by mixing their equimolar solutions with ligand and keeping the mixture in hot water for 1 h. The solutions on concentration precipitated the complexes which were washed and dried in vacuum desiccator. Magnesium and nickel complexes were precipitated from the equimolar mixed solution by adjusting pH of the solution below their pH of hydrolysis by adding required amount of dilute solution of NaOH. The complexes were washed and dried under reduced pressure.

The composition of metal complexes was ascertained by estimating carbon⁶, nitrogen⁷, hydrogen⁸ and the metal⁸ contents. Presence of lattice water was determined from the difference in the weight obtained on heating the complex to 120° .

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